

**D6.16 Report on OHEJP ASM
Satellite Workshop 2022**

WP6: Education and Training

Responsible Partner: UoS (P23)

GENERAL INFORMATION

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	OHEJP WP 4 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	OHEJP WP 5 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	OHEJP WP 6 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	OHEJP WP 7 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Project Management Team <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Communication Team <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Scientific Steering Board <input type="checkbox"/>	National Stakeholders/Program Owners Committee <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	EFSA <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	ECDC <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	EEA <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	EMA <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	FAO <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	WHO-EU <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	OIE <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Other international stakeholder(s):	Social Media:	Other recipient(s): Subscribers to OHEJP Education and Training monthly bulletin
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Introduction

The One Health EJP Annual Scientific Meeting (ASM) aims to highlight One Health based scientific advances within Joint Research Projects and Joint Integrative activities in the One Health EJP and other projects or initiatives. Each One Health EJP ASM event organises an accompanying relevant satellite workshop focusing on one of the priority areas of the One Health OHEJP. The 2022 One Health OHEJP ASM, Orvieto, Italy, 11th-13th April was a hybrid event facilitating both online and on-site options. The accompanying ASM satellite workshop “Diagnostics workshop: mobile detection platforms for One Health diagnostics applications” took place online on April 14th, 2022. This workshop focused on novel diagnostic technologies and mobile detection platforms for One Health applications.

Theme and Overview

The central theme of this OHEJP ASM satellite workshop was antimicrobial resistance (AMR) and novel diagnostic technologies focusing on the use of rapid and innovative methodologies for pathogen and AMR detection. The application and misuse of broad-spectrum antimicrobials has led to AMR becoming a leading global health concern. A key element of the One Health approach in combating the threat of AMR is surveillance of relevant biomarkers using novel diagnostic technologies to help monitor current resistance levels and associated health burdens. In addition, the rapid identification of emerging trends of clinical significance is of paramount importance. Loop-mediated isothermal amplification (LAMP) is a rapid, sensitive and specific nucleic acid amplification technology ideally suited the detection of AMR markers in both human hospital, veterinary and environmental settings. Loop-primer endonuclease cleavage-LAMP (LEC-LAMP) is a recently developed modification of LAMP that enables multiplex real-time pathogen detection with single-base specificity for AMR point-mutation detection.

Aims and Objectives

The aim of the OHEJP ASM satellite workshop was to facilitate training and discussion in the area of rapid and innovative nucleic acid diagnostic assay development for pathogen detection and AMR identification in both humans and animals. The workshop’s objectives were to discuss factors influencing the design of diagnostic assays for One Health applications, including sample types (environmental, medical or veterinary), target sequences and assay format, reflecting on current standard diagnostics in public and animal health. A second objective was to illustrate the background of two key mobile diagnostics platforms: LAMP and LEC-LAMP, their application in diagnostics, advantages compared to conventional assays and to discuss current challenges. The workshop also provided the opportunity for a hands-on *in-silico* approach to the design of diagnostic assays using LAMP and LEC-LAMP methods, with the focus on targeting zoonotic pathogens and AMR genes. This was an interactive event to facilitate learning and interactions among ECRs and PGRs and to discuss current and future diagnostics for One Health applications. There were opportunities for ECRs and PGRs to interact and discuss solutions for improving current One Health diagnostics and foster new collaborations.

Virtual Format

The 2022 One Health OHEJP ASM, Orvieto, Italy, was a hybrid event facilitating both online and on-site options. In keeping with this, the original plan was that the OHEJP ASM satellite workshop would also be a hybrid event, but there were some issues, so it was changed to an

online only event and this allowed more participants to be accommodated, facilitating a variety of talks and a hands-on practical session. Online workshop participation was facilitated using the Zoom platform with one-to-one interactions with speakers, panel members, workshop organisers and participants.

Programme Structure

**One Health EJP ASM Satellite Workshop:
Diagnostics workshop; mobile detection
platforms for One Health diagnostics applications
PROGRAMME**

Online: 14th April

CEST
09.30 *Welcome and housekeeping by Dr Marwa Hassan & Dr Owen Higgins*

09.40 **Rapid diagnostics for the detection of zoonotic pathogens and antimicrobial resistance**
Prof. Roberto La Ragione
Head of the School of Biosciences and Medicine and Professor of Veterinary Microbiology and Pathology, University of Surrey

10.00 **The use of comparative genomics in diagnostics for One Health applications**
Dr. Arnoud van Vliet
Senior lecturer in Microbiology, School of Veterinary Medicine, University of Surrey

10.30 **Molecular detection in public health, animal health and environmental applications**
Dr. Louise O'Connor
Senior Technical Officer, School of Medicine, National University of Ireland, Galway

11.00 **Coffee Break**
Open discussions among participants on One Health diagnostics from a multidisciplinary perspective

11.30 **How diagnostics can help current challenges in One Health applications and risk management**
Dr. Dan Horton
Associate Dean Research and Innovation and Reader in Veterinary Virology, School of Veterinary Medicine, University of Surrey

12.00 **Introduction to LAMP detection and its applications**
Dr. Aurore Poirier
Postdoctoral research fellow, School of Veterinary Medicine, University of Surrey

12.30 **Introduction to LEC-LAMP detection and its applications**
Dr. Owen Higgins
Postdoctoral research fellow, School of Natural Sciences, National University of Ireland, Galway

13.00 **Lunch Break**

14.00 **One Health diagnostics discussion on other platforms, applications, future directions, collaborations within OHEJP JRPs and Closing remarks for discussions**
Panel of the speakers

15.00 **Hands-on Workshop**
Designing LAMP and LEC-LAMP assays workshop
Dr. Marwa Hassan
Postdoctoral research fellow, School of Veterinary Medicine, University of Surrey
Dr. Owen Higgins
Postdoctoral research fellow, School of Natural Sciences, National University of Ireland, Galway

17.00 **Close**

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Experts and Speakers

Prof. Roberto La Ragione, Head of School of Biosciences and Medicine and Professor of Veterinary Microbiology and Pathology in the School of Veterinary Medicine at the University

of Surrey introduced the topic of rapid diagnostics for detection of zoonotic pathogens and antimicrobial resistance.

Dr. Arnoud van Vliet, Senior Lecturer in Microbiology in the School of Veterinary Medicine at the University of Surrey introduced the use of comparative genomics in diagnostics for One Health applications.

Dr. Louise O'Connor, Senior Technical Officer in the School of Medicine at the National University of Ireland, Galway, presented on molecular diagnostics in public health, animal health and environmental applications.

Dr. Dan Horton, Associate Dean for Research and Innovation and Reader in Veterinary Virology in the School of Veterinary Medicine at the University of Surrey presented on the use of diagnostics used to meet current challenges in One Health applications.

Dr. Aurore Poirier, a postdoctoral research Fellow in the School of Veterinary Medicine at the University of Surrey gave an introduction to LAMP detection and its applications.

Dr. Owen Higgins, a postdoctoral research Fellow in the School of Natural Sciences at the University of Galway introduced the topic of LEC-LAMP detection and its applications.

Dr. Marwa Hassan, a postdoctoral research Fellow in the School of Veterinary Medicine at the University of Surrey conducted an interactive workshop detailing the designing of LAMP assays.

Working Group Tutors

Dr. Marwa Hassan, a postdoctoral research Fellow in the School of Veterinary Medicine at the University of Surrey, and Dr. Owen Higgins, a postdoctoral research Fellow in the School of Natural Sciences at the University of Galway, conducted an interactive design workshop focusing on LAMP and LEC-LAMP assay design incorporating various participant tasks with questions and answer session to facilitate direct applications to their interests and they also closed the workshop.

Logistical arrangements

The virtual format was supported by the conference platform and access to the Zoom webinar. Participants received a link to join the event in a timely manner, a streamline was also displayed on the conference event link. All access issues were resolved by the LEO/LOC with support from the conference IT members. Additionally, participants of the hands-on session received some reading materials including up-to-date published papers in the field of diagnostics to provide some directions and enrich the discussions.

Promotional Campaign

The promotional campaign was managed by the OHEJP Communications Team. A 'Save the Date' promotional flyer (Annex 1) was created and validated with the ASM satellite workshop organising team.

This flyer was promoted and distributed through the OHEJP channels: the OHEJP website with latest new post shared on April 8th 2022, the OHEJP social media channels of Twitter and LinkedIn with posts frequently disseminated (weekly to fortnightly) between November 2021

to April 2022, and the Consortium Newsletters of December 2021 and March 2022. [A dedicated satellite workshop webpage](#) was created in December 2021. The [ASM 2022 website](#) also had a dedicated [page for the ASM satellite workshop](#) with key information and links to the ASM satellite workshop page on the OHEJP website. The registration for the workshop opened on 8th December 2021 and closed on 15th February 2022. Calls for registration were disseminated on OHEJP social media channels and via email.

Once the details of the ASM satellite workshop programme had been confirmed, a detailed full promotional flyer (Annex 2) and an event programme (Annex 3) were created and validated with the ASM satellite workshop organising team.

The flyer and programme were uploaded on the OHEJP satellite workshop webpage and promoted through the OHEJP social media channels. Short biographies and photos of the confirmed presenters were added to the website page as they were received.

Applications and selection procedure

As the workshop was online, all applications received were accepted. Additional participants requested joining after the deadline and those were also accepted. In total, we accepted 99 participants to the workshop and had 7 speakers.

Delegates

Participants were mostly from all OHEJP partner institutes and countries with some representation from the industry sector. They were from all educational backgrounds, students, research fellows (experienced and unexperienced in molecular diagnostics) and group leaders that had interest in molecular diagnostics and the application to One Health. Three VIP places were taken by stakeholders.

Highest Educational Level

102 responses

Educational Background

102 responses

Course Evaluation

After completion of the satellite workshop all participants were provided with an event evaluation form generated and collected by the University of Surrey. Overall, attendees were satisfied with the event, the range of expert speakers and the hands-on workshop. They enjoyed learning about rapid diagnostics and their One Health applications and found the workshop useful and relevant. All participants stated that they would attend a similar workshop organised by the One Health EJP.

Certificates of Attendance

Certificates of attendance were generated by the University of Surrey and electronic copies were provide to participants who requested a certificate post event.

Post-event communications

Blog Post

The OHEJP communications team created branded visual montages from the screenshots and testimonials. These montages were used to report and share the success of the workshop through the One Health EJP social media channels Twitter and LinkedIn. A blog post was created on the [One Health EJP blog](#) on the website.

Testimonials

Anonymous testimonials were collected by the ASM organising team, through the event evaluation process. Permission to publish the received testimonials was obtained during the process.

Examples of Delegate Testimonials collected

Information to share the success of the workshop was disseminated in social media posts in April, with the testimonials shared in a social media post on 27th April 2022.

Newsletters

Articles highlighting the success of the workshop were disseminated in the Consortium Newsletter June 2022 and the External Newsletter June 2022.

Photos

Permission to publish these photos was obtained during the event registration process. The face and names of any participants or lecturers who had not provided permission were blurred out to adhere to the GDPR regulations.

Highlights video

Permission to publish the photos, recordings and testimonials were obtained, and adhere to GDPR regulations.

Internal Events Survey information

The European Commission (EC) requires all dissemination and communication activities, and events to be reported. This information has been reported through the [Internal Events Survey](#) on the OHEJP website, which collects data and is reported to the EC.

Name of the activity:	OHEJP ASM Satellite Workshop 2022		
Date:	14 th April 2022		
Place:	Orvieto, Italy		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference	No	Participation to a Conference	No
Organisation of a Workshop	Yes	Participation to a Workshop	No
Press release	No	Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	No
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)	No	Video/Film	No
Exhibition	No	Brokerage Event	
Flyer	Yes	Pitch Event	No
Training	Yes	Trade Fair	No
Social Media	Yes	Participation in activities organised jointly with other H2020 projects	No
Website	Yes	Other	No
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)	No		
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	106	Media	0
Industry	0	Investors	0
Civil Society	0	Customers	0
General Public	0	Other	0
Policy Makers	3		

Annex 1: "Save the Date" Promotional Flyer

Save the Date!
One Health EJP
Annual Scientific Meeting Satellite Workshop:
Diagnostics workshop: mobile detection platforms
for One Health diagnostics applications

Date:
14th April 2022

Location:
Online

Audience:
PhD students, early career researchers and scientists with an interest in One Health-related diagnostic applications are highly welcome.

Fee:
Free to attend

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Annex 2: Full Promotional Flyer

One Health EJP
Annual Scientific Meeting Satellite Workshop:
Diagnostics workshop: mobile detection platforms
for One Health diagnostics applications

Date:
14th April 2022

Location:
Hybrid event, online and in person Orvieto, Italy

Audience:
PhD students, early career researchers and scientists with an interest in One Health-related diagnostic applications are highly welcome.

Fee:
Free to attend

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#OHEJPASM2022

What is the aim of the ASM Satellite Diagnostic Workshop?

The aim of the workshop is to facilitate training and discussion in the area of rapid and innovative diagnostics development for pathogens and antimicrobial resistance for use in both human and animals.

The workshop's objectives are to discuss factors influencing the design of diagnostic assays for One Health applications, including sample types (environmental, medical or veterinary), target sequences and assay format, reflecting on current standard diagnostics in public and animal health. A second objective will be to illustrate the background of two key mobile diagnostics platforms: LAMP and LEC-LAMP, their application in diagnostics, advantages compared to conventional assays and to discuss current challenges. LAMP is a rapid loop-mediated isothermal amplification approach to detect target nucleic acids; while LEC-LAMP is a recently developed modified LAMP assay that can facilitate single nucleotide polymorphism (SNP) identification and the multiplex target detection.

The workshop will also provide the opportunity for a hands-on *in-silico* approach to the design of diagnostic assays using LAMP and LEC-LAMP platforms, with the focus on targeting zoonotic pathogens and antimicrobial resistance genes.

This will be an interactive event to facilitate learning and interactions among ECRs and PGRs and will discuss current and future diagnostics for One Health applications. There will be opportunities for ECRs and PGRs to interact and discuss solutions for improving current One Health diagnostics and foster new collaborations.

Register [here](#).

Registration closes at 12 midnight CET on 15th February 2022.

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Annex 3: Event Programme

One Health EJP ASM Satellite Workshop: Diagnostics workshop; mobile detection platforms for One Health diagnostics applications PROGRAMME

Online: 14th April

CEST

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Panel of the speakers

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Designing LAMP and LEC-LAMP assays workshop

Dr. Marwa Hassan

Postdoctoral research fellow, School of Veterinary Medicine, University of Surrey

Dr. Owen Higgins

Postdoctoral research fellow, School of Natural Sciences, National University of Ireland, Galway

17.00 *Close*

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